

Industrialized Agriculture in Europe: A Threat to the Balance of Sustainability

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Abstract

The industrialization of agriculture in Europe has profoundly changed food production and, at the same time, created significant environmental, social and economic challenges. This paper analyzes the impact of this transformation on the balance between the three pillars of sustainability - environmental, social and economic - and examines the extent to which EU policies, such as the European Green Deal, counteract this imbalance. The paper is based on a qualitative literature review of scientific reports, studies and policy documents. The results show that industrialization is advancing in favor of economic interests, while ecological and social aspects are often neglected, which contributes to the emergence of unsustainable structures. The main victims are people from poorer and/or rural regions, the environment and animals of all kinds. EU policy approaches formulate ambitious goals, but often fail due to a lack of implementation and a lack of coherence between the member states. The Essay highlights the need to focus more on environmental and social concerns in agricultural policy in order to ensure a fairer and more sustainable future for European agriculture.

Keywords

Industrialization of agriculture, Sustainability, European agricultural policy, Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), European Green Deal, Animal welfare, Ecological impact, Social justice, Rural society

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1. Introduction

The industrialization of agriculture has revolutionized food production and enables cost-effective and mass-oriented food procurement. At the same time, however, it also brings with it a multitude of challenges and raises questions of social and climate justice. Originally characterized by small family farms, European agriculture has developed into large-scale industrial structures through mechanization, intensification and globalization (BMEL, 2024). This development has not only ecological, but also social and economic effects that require critical consideration.

This essay uses the model of the three pillars of sustainability (ecological, social and economic sustainability) to critically scrutinize the current state of European agriculture.

At the center of this essay is the question of how the transformation of agriculture influences the balance between the three pillars of sustainability, and to what extent it contributes to the emergence of unsustainable structures in Europe. The measures taken by EU policy to counteract this imbalance are then examined on a smaller scale. It can be assumed that the industrialization of agriculture in Europe is shifting the balance between the three pillars of sustainability in favor of economic interests and that the EU's existing political measures are not sufficient to significantly compensate for the negative consequences of this development.

To answer these questions empirically, a qualitative literature review was conducted in accordance with Mayring (2019). Thereby, relevant scientific papers, reports and policy documents were analyzed and contextually merged (Mayring & Fenzl, 2019, pp. 636-637) to identify the environmental, social and economic impacts of industrial agriculture as well as the effectiveness of policy measures.

The essay is divided into four thematic blocks: First, the theoretical concept of the three pillars of sustainability is presented. This is followed by a detailed examination of the industrialization of agriculture and its effects, divided into the areas of environment, animals and society. The following chapter contains an analytical discussion in which the three dimensions of agricultural sustainability in Europe are critically evaluated. Finally, there is a rough summary and evaluation of EU policy measures aimed at promoting sustainable development in Europe.

This structure enables a comprehensive analysis of the challenges and opportunities associated with the industrialization of agriculture in Europe and can provide a basis for future discussions and policy decisions.

2. The Three Pillars of Sustainability

The “three pillars of sustainability” model provides a general perspective on the fundamental goals of sustainability. It comprises the three dimensions of “ecological sustainability”, “social sustainability”, and “economic sustainability”, which should be in balance with each other in order to enable a sustainable future (GoClimate, 2022; Purvis et al., 2019, pp. 682, 685). In politics, sustainability is generally defined as a concept that meets the needs of today's generation, without threatening the opportunities of future generations (German Parliament, n.d.).

The **ecological pillar** focuses on the protection and preservation of the natural basis of life, nature and the responsible use of resources. The aim is to stabilize natural cycles in the long term. The key aspects here are the conservation of resources, preservation of biodiversity, reduction of emissions and waste, and pollutant management. This pillar forms the basis for the other two pillars, because both social and economic structures are dependent on an intact environment (GoClimate, 2022; Kropp, 2019, p. 11).

The **social pillar** mainly addresses the aspects of social justice, co-determination, strengthening community, cultural diversity and identity. It is about ensuring that all people benefit from developments and are included in decision-making processes in order to improve or maintain their individual quality of life (GoClimate, 2022; Kropp, 2019, p. 11).

The third and final pillar is the **economical pillar**. In the context of sustainability, the focus here is on creating a long-term viable economy that does not function at the expense of the environment or society. The core objectives here are to create jobs and prosperity while at the same time respecting ecological limits (GoClimate, 2022; Kropp, 2019, p. 11).

The approach has no specific origin, but has developed in the discourse on sustainability. Where the idea first emerged is therefore disputed. However, it was first presented visually in 1987 by Barbier (Purvis et al., 2019, p. 682). Back then, the three dimensions were presented as being of equal value and should be in constant balance with each other (GoClimate, 2022).

The theoretical basis of the model is controversial, as there is no coherent theoretical basis for the assumption that the three dimensions must be in balance with each other in order to guarantee sustainability. This situation makes it difficult to apply the model in the policy development process (GoClimate, 2022; Purvis et al., 2019, pp. 682-684, 689-690). Nevertheless, the concept forms a comprehensible basis in the theoretical discourse on sustainability (Purvis et al., 2019, p. 690) and is therefore suitable for this theoretical analysis.

In this essay, the model is used as an analytical framework to examine the impact of the industrialization of agriculture on the ecological, economic and social balance in Europe and to assess its contribution to the emergence of unsustainable structures. However, it is consistently treated critically and as non-infallible.

3. The Industrialization of Agriculture and Its Impacts

3.1. The Development of Agriculture in Europe

Since the **18th century**, European agriculture has undergone a profound transformation from small-scale family farms to industrialized mass production (Nienaber, 2012, p. 253).

The so-called “agricultural revolution” began in England in the 18th century and spread across Western Europe until the **19th century**. This revolution led to the transition from self-sufficiency to market production, which in turn led to an increase in agricultural productivity. This laid the foundation for the subsequent industrialization of agriculture (Nienaber, 2012, pp. 253-254).

At the beginning of the **20th century**, tractors and other machines became established and increasingly replaced manual labor, which led to a considerable increase in efficiency. At the same

time, the use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides increased in order to achieve higher yields. Thus, began the era of mechanization and intensification. These developments fostered the intensification of production and the specialization of companies (Mahlerwein, 2020). In 1962, the European Economic Community introduced the “Common Agricultural Policy” (CAP), which aimed to increase productivity and ensure security of supply. Incentives for further intensification and expansion were created through subsidies and price support, which accelerated the structural change towards larger farms (Weingarten, 2021).

At the end of the 20th century and the beginning of the **21st century**, the trend towards larger farms continued, while the overall number of farms declined. In Germany, for example, the number of farms has halved since the mid-1990s, with smaller farms being particularly affected (BMEL, 2024). Between 2005 and 2013, the number of farms in the EU fell by around 3.7% per year, resulting in the disappearance of 1.2 million farms. At the same time, the average farm size has increased as larger farms take over the land that has become available and expand their production capacities (European Parliament, 2016, pp. 6-7).

3.2. Environmental Impacts

The concentration on larger farms leads to more intensive and efficient production (BMEL, 2024), but also raises concerns about environmental and social sustainability.

The industrialization of agriculture and the intensive livestock farming have far-reaching ecological consequences. The food industry is responsible for around 21-37% of greenhouse gas emissions (Stucki, 2023). Within the EU, this corresponds to approximately 1,012 million tons of greenhouse gas (Wilke, 2013a). Methane (CH₄) is a particularly potent greenhouse gas. It is mainly released through the digestion of ruminants such as cattle, which is a key contributor to the fact that the dairy and meat industries are responsible for around 80% of emissions in the agricultural sector (Stucki, 2023; Wilke, 2013b). If nothing changes in terms of emissions due to production in the livestock industry, the temperature would rise by 0.32 °C by 2050 purely as a result of meat and milk production (Greenpeace, 2024, p. 1).

The overuse of water is another factor that contributes to the unsustainability of agriculture. Irrigation of intensive agricultural crops can lead to falling groundwater levels and the drying out of wetlands, which in turn has a negative impact on local ecosystems. The livestock industry also performs particularly poorly in terms of water consumption: on average, up to 15,500 liters of water are required to produce 1 kg of beef. By comparison, around 320 liters of water are used to produce 1 kg of vegetables (Hoekstra, 2010, pp. 19-23; PETA, 2023).

The use of synthetic fertilizers and pesticides leads to the contamination of groundwater and surface water. Pesticide residues thus contribute to the deterioration of water quality (Feindt et al., 2019, pp. 34-36). In addition, the increased use of pesticides impairs soil structure and health, which in turn leads to reduced soil fertility and a significant decline in biodiversity (Feindt et al., 2019, pp. 24-29). In Germany, for example, populations of farmland birds have fallen by more than half in the last 40 years. Similar trends can be seen in insects and plant species (Bucher, 2024).

Mass production, especially of meat, leads to an increase in the production of animal feed, such as soy, which in turn leads to the deforestation of (tropical) forests. This deforestation destroys the natural habitat of many animal species and also releases stored carbon. The result is an unparalleled extinction of species and the acceleration of global warming (WWF, 2014, pp. 9-10).

As much space as the animal industry takes up, there is not much room left for the animals, which brings us to the issue of animal exploitation.

3.3. Exploitation of Animals

Mass production in agriculture not only destroys the habitat of countless local wild animals, but also has serious consequences for billions of cattle, pigs and chickens every year. According to estimates by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), global meat production increased by 26% between 2013 and 2023. Every year, around 70 billion animals are slaughtered worldwide to meet the demand for animal products (FAO, 2024, pp. 10-13). The EU is responsible for several billion of these slaughtered animals (Schlachthof transparent, n.d.).

The EU provides the legal framework for the member states for most of the legal minimum standards in factory farming. According to the EU directive, each fattening pig is entitled to an area of 0.15 square meters to 1.00 square meters, depending on its weight (COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 2008/120/EC of 18 December 2008 Laying down Minimum Standards for the Protection of Pigs, 2008, p. 2). These movement restrictions and the lack of exercise often lead to musculoskeletal disorders and behavioral disorders (Albert Schweitzer Stiftung für unsere Mitwelt, 2024; WWF, 2023).

Around 154 million tons of cow's milk were produced in the EU in 2023 (European Commission, 2024a). To ensure such a quantity, dairy cows are bred to produce five times the amount of milk they would normally give. This high-performance pressure and constant milking lead to severe udder infections (mastitis), which are then treated with antibiotics. However, milk production is not stopped during treatment or during pregnancy, which means that antibiotic residues also end up in dairy products (Deutscher Tierschutzbund e.V., n.d.). In 2019, almost 670 tons of antibiotics were used for this purpose (PETA, 2024). To ensure that milk production does not stop as soon as the calf reaches weaning age, the cow is inseminated again a few weeks after giving birth. This process continues for an average of 5 years until the animals are slaughtered because they are no longer profitable. The actual life expectancy of the animals is 20 years (PETA, 2024). When a female calf is born, she faces the same life as her mother. Male calves are usually transported abroad from the age of 14 days to be fattened and slaughtered (Deutscher Tierschutzbund e.V., n.d.; PETA, 2024).

The conditions of industrialized agriculture and factory farming not only have a negative impact on animals and the environment. The methods used in factory farming and the climatic consequences of the agricultural industry are causally linked to people's health and well-being (WHO, 2023).

3.4. Impacts on Society

The industrialization of agriculture in Europe has a profound impact on the health and well-being of people, especially farmers and rural communities. These effects manifest themselves on both a physical and psychological level and promote social inequalities.

The obvious risks to human health are pesticide residues in groundwater caused by fertilization or antibiotic residues in animal products (Feindt et al., 2019, pp. 34-36; PETA, 2024). However, there are also effects that are less discussed:

According to a study by Paris Lodron University in Salzburg, around 46% of all farmers (in Germany and Austria) suffer from burnout, depression or anxiety. According to the study, the main causes of this are a high workload, financial insecurity and social pressure (Roth, 2021, pp. 38-39, 66-67). The suicide rate among (French) farmers is around 20% higher than in the average population (INA, 2024).

The industrialization of agriculture favours large farms and displaces small-scale farming structures. This leads to social inequality and alienation of the rural population. As a result of such developments, small farmers are often forced to give up their farms (Nachhaltigkeit Wirtschaft, 2024). This and the dominance of global companies lead to traditional agricultural practices being displaced and the social structure of rural communities being impaired. This leads to rural exodus, the alienation of rural societies, and ultimately to the social and economic weakening of rural areas. The dominance of a few large players in the agricultural sector therefore weakens the economic diversity and resilience of rural regions (Baur, 2013; VSF International, 2024, pp. 1-3).

Climate change also has a direct impact on people's lives and health. Heatwaves, fires, droughts and floods are also taking away people's living space, which means that many people have to leave their homes (European Union, n.d.). In 2023, 26.4 million people had to leave their homes due to natural disasters. That is around 6 million more refugees than those displaced by conflict and violence (iDMC, 2024, pp. 9, 11).

The previously discussed social effects of agricultural industrialization illustrate the need to critically question the balance between ecological, social and economic sustainability in Europe.

4. Analytical Discussion

4.1. Ecological Sustainability

The developments and effects of the industrialization of agriculture in Europe described above form the basis for the following analytical discussion, in which the ecological, social and economic dimensions of sustainability are examined and their balance in the European context is critically evaluated.

As described in the previous chapters, industrial agriculture has a significant impact on environmental sustainability. According to the three pillars of sustainability model, the ecological dimension should form the basis for the other two pillars, as nature is also the basis for social and economic activity (GoClimate, 2022; Kropp, 2019, p. 11). However, in view of developments in recent decades, the environmental aspect seems to have been pushed into the background. More focus has been placed on efficiency, productivity and profit, which in retrospect has had disastrous consequences for the climate and life on earth (Feindt et al., 2019, pp. 34-36; Greenpeace, 2024). Fundamental climate targets, such as the goal that global warming should not exceed 1.5 degrees Celsius (Paris Climate Agreement 2015), have already been missed (Bültena, 2025). As agriculture is responsible for a considerable proportion of highly potent greenhouse gases, it makes a significant contribution to global warming (Stucki, 2023).

The overuse of water and soil resources and the resulting negative impacts on natural habitats and biodiversity also tend to be counterproductive for a healthy environment as a basis for life (Feindt et al., 2019, pp. 24-29).

In summarized terms, the analysis shows that the ecological pillar is often subordinated to economic interests in practice. The practices of profit-focused agriculture undermine the aim of stabilizing natural cycles and contradict the requirements of ecological sustainability.

4.2. Social Sustainability

According to the theory, social sustainability should ensure aspects such as social justice, cultural diversity and community empowerment (GoClimate, 2022; Kropp, 2019, p. 11). By taking social aspects into account, fair structures in food procurement and within the industry should be established in the long term. In practice, however, the industrialization of agriculture shows the opposite tendencies.

Subsidies and market mechanisms favor large farms, which increases economic inequality and pushes out small farms (Nachhaltigkeit Wirtschaft, 2024). The development of agriculture towards a highly capitalist system with tendencies towards monopoly formation leads to existential fears and great social and financial pressure for a large number of farmers. This leads to social alienation and a loss of cultural identity in rural areas (Nachhaltigkeit Wirtschaft, 2024; Roth, 2021, pp. 38-39, 66-67).

The focus on mass production and standardized production methods is displacing traditional agricultural practices. These developments undermine the quality of life and social stability of rural communities and are at odds with the principles of social sustainability, which emphasize diversity and participation (Baur, 2013; VSF International, 2024, pp. 1-3).

Social injustice is also caused by climate change, for which the agricultural sector is one of the most responsible. Around the world, the countries most affected by climate change tend to be those that contribute the least (Beltermann et al., 2022). This results in millions of climate refugees every year, who often find themselves in life-threatening situations due to their displacement and are affected by poverty in the long term (Statista, 2023).

Animal welfare can also be considered within the social dimension, as EU law actually stipulates that animals are a part of our society worthy of protection (Art. 13 AEUV, n.d.). However, practice once again shows the opposite. In the animal industry, the focus is primarily on productivity and profit, which leads to animal welfare being neglected (WWF, 2023).

The analysis shows that the industrialization of agriculture undermines the principles of social sustainability by increasing economic inequalities, displacing traditional agricultural practices, and affecting the quality of life and social stability of rural communities.

4.3. Economic Sustainability

Due to the fact that the agricultural sector has become highly capitalized, the focus is fundamentally on the economic aspects (BMEL, 2024). At first glance, the economy benefits the most from this development. However, the economic pillar is not necessarily about a strong, superior economy but primarily about creating prosperity without causing ecological or social costs (Go-Climate, 2022; Kropp, 2019, p. 11).

Nevertheless, the fact that large, monopolistic corporations lead the agricultural sector does not necessarily lead to social prosperity - on the contrary. A well-known example is the Swiss food company Nestlé. In 2023, Nestlé had a turnover of 93 billion Swiss francs (approx. 86.5 billion euros) (Ahrens, 2024). In Switzerland itself, the high number of large corporations is beneficial for its own economy (Swiss Holdings, 2012, p. 5). However, especially in the case of Nestlé, this is done without regard for global social and climatic losses. The company is regularly responsible for scandals such as child labor, resource exploitation, modern slave labor, climate exploitation and the displacement of small farmers (Hackbarth, 2024; humanrights.ch, 2005; Public Eye, 2024, pp. 6-7). Nestlé has been criticized for years for privatizing and commercially exploiting water resources worldwide. This approach often leads to a drop in groundwater levels and local communities having difficulties gaining access to clean drinking water. The population is forced to buy back their own water at inflated prices, which exacerbates social inequalities (Tillich, 2017). A significant proportion of profits result from unequal power relations in the supply chain, which put small producers at a disadvantage. Farmers complain that they are kept in dependency and poverty by low prices and poor pay. These practices exacerbate social inequalities and force many producers to abandon their farms (Public Eye, 2024, pp. 6-7, 19-20).

Furthermore, monocultures and intensive production methods lead to a short-term increase in profits, but in the long term they threaten the stability of agricultural production through ecosystem damage and climate risks (Feindt et al., 2019, 24-29, 34-36).

A look at the current state of the agricultural sector shows that the original idea of creating a strong economy within the economic dimension without causing climatic or social losses is currently not the case. Instead, mass production and the formation of monopolies are leading to

people suffering from the loss of basic human rights, the exploitation of billions of animals every year and, in addition, devastating climatic consequences.

In summary, the current agricultural economy is not sustainable and almost exclusively favors the large corporations themselves.

4.4. The Imbalance of European Sustainability

As the previous chapters have shown, the agricultural sector does not currently meet the criteria for long-term sustainable and fair food procurement. The analysis shows that there is currently no balance between the three pillars in the EU. Economic interests often dominate at the expense of ecological and social dimensions. These imbalances lead to a reinforcement of unsustainable structures. In addition to the environment, people from poorer countries, rural areas and animals of all kinds suffer the most from this industry (Beltermann et al., 2022; Public Eye, pp. 6-7, 2024; Stucki, 2023; WWF, 2023).

It can therefore be concluded that the three pillars of sustainability in relation to European industrialized agriculture are currently not in balance with each other. In this context, however, the model could be critically questioned by asking whether an absolute balance makes sense at all. Some authors, such as Passet (1979) and Macnaghten and Jacobs (1997) argue that the three pillars should not be considered equal. Instead, the economy should operate within social and environmental boundaries. This is also referred to as the “nested model”, where the economy is subordinate to the environment and society (Purvis et al., 2019, pp. 687-689). As also described in the three-pillar model, an intact society and a healthy environment are the basis for a functioning economy in the long term. If we focus almost exclusively on the economic component, as is currently the case, climate damage and social injustice will very likely also have a negative impact on the economy and prosperity in the future (GoClimate, 2022; Kropp, 2019, p. 11-12).

Economic sustainability must therefore not be viewed in isolation. Sustainable agriculture requires better integration of the environmental and social dimensions in order to ensure long-term stability.

The EU is also concerned about these aspects and has passed several laws in recent years that are intended to put European agriculture on a more sustainable path, whereby the ecological, social and economic dimensions should ultimately be linked more closely and uncompromisingly.

5. Political Actions Against the Imbalance

5.1. The European Green Deal

Looking back over the last few years, the EU appears to be aware of the unsustainable structures in the European agricultural sector, as a number of rules and regulations have already been adopted to address this imbalance.

The largest and most complex of these political measures is the “**European Green Deal**” (EGD). Numerous new regulations are being introduced, or existing regulations are being reformed under it. The European Green Deal, launched in 2019, seeks to make the EU climate-neutral by 2050 and promote social justice at the same time (European Council, 2019).

For agriculture, the “**Farm-to-Fork Strategy**” (F2F) plays a central role in promoting sustainability, healthy food systems, and reduced resource use (European Commission, 2020, pp. 4-8). Objectives include cutting pesticide use by 50%, increasing organic farming to 25% of agricultural land, and reducing food waste (European Commission, 2020, pp. 8-15, 20).

One part of the F2F strategy relevant to this essay is the “**EU Animal Welfare Strategy**”. It was decided to rework key regulations by 2023 in order to further raise animal welfare standards (European Commission, 2022b, p. 1). In order to make these upgrades effectively, the “**Fitness Check**” was carried out in 2020 to assess whether the existing regulations are “fit” for purpose, efficient and coherent (European Commission, 2022b, pp. 1-2). Key findings revealed outdated laws, insufficient monitoring indicators, and gaps in species-specific welfare, especially for dairy cows and farmed fish (European Commission, 2022, pp. 2-3; Gavinelli, 2013, p. 11). The Check is intended to help adapt key legislation to new scientific findings and social expectations (European Commission, 2022b, pp. 1-2).

Another part of the European Green Deal is the reform of the **Common Agricultural Policy** (CAP) from 1962, which originally aimed to increase agricultural productivity, ensure food security, and stabilize farmers income post-war (European Commission, 2024b). The 2023-2027 CAP emphasizes green, fair, and innovative agriculture, allocating 307 billion Euros to promote sustainability and rural development (European Commission, 2022a, p. 2; 2023, p. 1). Key measures include stricter conditions for direct payments, such as compliance with environmental and animal welfare standards. Furthermore, at least 10% of payments are redistributed to smaller farms, to encourage competitive and social justice (European Commission, 2022, pp. 6, 8; 2023, pp. 4-7). Measures like reducing pesticide use, protecting moors and grasslands, and promoting low-emission practices aim to align the CAP with climate protection goals (European Commission, 2023, pp. 5-6). The regulations no longer only refer to increasing productivity, but also combine economic, social and ecological aspects. With a budget of 307 billion euros, the CAP 2023-2027 is a central component of the European Green Deal (European Commission, 2022, p. 2; 2023, p. 1).

5.2. Evaluation of the Political Measures

In principle, even the smallest step towards sustainable agriculture contributes to social and climate justice. However, the European Green Deal has weaknesses, especially when it comes to the consistency and appropriateness of the individual measures.

The EGD sets ambitious targets, such as the goal that the EU should be climate-neutral by 2025. However, it has particular weaknesses when it comes to implementation in the individual member states. Many member states have difficulties integrating the targets into national strategies. In addition, the EU lacks control mechanisms, which means that implementation in the individual states varies greatly in some cases. The EU Commission has repeatedly stated that this lack

of harmonization significantly limits the effectiveness of the CAP. This is particularly evident in the decline in biodiversity, which could not be significantly curbed despite many reforms and new regulations (Heyl et al., 2021, p. 97, 104; Pe'er et al., 2022, pp. 5-8).

Despite the CAP's regulations on fairer redistribution of direct payments, large farms are still the main recipients of these subsidies. This increases social injustice and also contributes to a poorer environmental balance, as large corporations cause significantly more environmental damage than small businesses (Pe'er et al., 2022, pp. 2-3).

However, it is important to say that the regulations offer important potential for sustainable and fair agriculture. Nevertheless, there is a lack of consistent implementation and, in some cases, a certain radicalism, as a rapid reform of the system is urgently needed in order to contain the consequences of climate change as far as possible (Fetting, 2020, p. 19; Fusco, 2021, p. 13; Heyl et al., 2021, p. 103).

Animal protection laws are not just a question of effectiveness but, above all, a question of ethics. The EU's existing animal welfare laws, including requirements for minimum housing areas, have long been criticized by animal welfare organizations and ethics experts. Despite regulations, animals suffer from mental and physical illnesses due to the way they are kept. The practice of "humane slaughter" also remains ethically controversial. In its opinion, the German Ethics Council emphasizes that the term "humane" obscures the fundamental ethical issue of the targeted killing of animals. Even under the best conditions, the death of animals remains an infringement of their right to life and is primarily motivated by economic interests (German Ethics Council, 2020, pp. 57-63; Kubon, 2022).

6. Conclusion

The analysis has shown that the industrialization of European agriculture has led to an enormous increase in productivity, but at the expense of the environment, animals and social justice. The result is a considerable imbalance in the social, ecological and economic dimensions and thus the development of unsustainable and unjust structures. In retrospect, the EU's political measures have also focused on increasing profits and efficiency. However, as part of the European Green Deal, the EU has shown a willingness to counteract this imbalance in recent years. But here too, a closer look shows that these approaches are often implemented inconsistently and remain limited in their impact.

The research questions can therefore be answered as follows: Industrialization shifts the balance of the three pillars in favor of economic interests, while ecological and social aspects are often neglected. This development has led to the emergence of unsustainable structures that jeopardize the long-term preservation of resources and social stability. EU policy is attempting to restore the balance with instruments such as the CAP and the Farm-to-Fork Strategy. The goals are ambitious. However, there is a lack of consistent implementation and harmonization of the measures between the member states, which severely limits their effectiveness. The results of this essay therefore largely confirm the hypothesis put forward.

The methodical approach of literature research proved to be effective for this essay. Nevertheless, when writing the essay, profound (ethical) questions arose, particularly with regard to the animal issue, which could not be elaborated on in greater depth within the scope of this work. The evaluation of the political measures is also only a superficial elaboration. This could be supplemented in future work in order to further validate the results.

The results of this work show the need for greater integration of environmental and social aspects into European agricultural policy. A sustainable future for agriculture requires not only ambitious political goals, but also their consistent and binding implementation. At the same time, there should be a stronger focus on the intrinsic value of animals and the protection of rural communities in order to create a fairer and more sustainable agriculture.

7. Bibliography

- Ahrens, S. (2024, April 24). *Umsatz von Nestlé weltweit bis 2023*. Statista. <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/160308/umfrage/umsatz-des-nestle-konzerns-weltweit-seit-2005/>
- Albert Schweitzer Stiftung für unsere Mitwelt. (2024). *Mastschweine • Albert Schweitzer Stiftung für unsere Mitwelt*. Albert Schweitzer Stiftung für unsere Mitwelt. <https://albertschweitzer-stiftung.de/massentierhaltung/schweine/mastschweine>
- Art. 13 AEUV. Retrieved 15 January 2025, from <https://dejure.org/gesetze/AEUV/13.html>
- Baur, N. (2013, April 10). Globale Unternehmen und lokale Lebensverhältnisse. Der Einfluss der räumlichen Organisation der Produktion auf die Gesellschaft – SozBlog. *Soziologie Blog*. <https://blog.soziologie.de/2013/04/globale-unternehmen-und-lokale-lebensverhaeltnisse-der-einfluss-der-raumlichen-organisation-der-produktion-auf-die-gesellschaft/>
- Beltermann et al. (2022, February 2). *Fragen der Verantwortung: Wer das Klima am meisten schädigt – und wer die Folgen trägt*. Tagesspiegel. <https://interaktiv.tagesspiegel.de/lab/klimawandel-afrika-welt-wer-das-klima-schaedigt-und-wer-die-folgen-traegt/>
- BMEL. (2024). *Betriebsstruktur und Entwicklung*. BMEL-Statistik. <https://bmel-statistik.de/landwirtschaft/landwirtschaftliche-betriebe/betriebsstruktur-und-entwicklung>
- Bucher, M. (2024, October 11). *Artenvielfalt in Deutschland: Schlecht steht es um Vögel und Insekten – das hat vor allem einen Grund - WELT*. DIE WELT. <https://www.welt.de/wissenschaft/article253777654/Artenvielfalt-in-Deutschland-Schlecht-steht-es-um-Voegel-und-Insekten-das-hat-vor-allem-einen-Grund.html>
- Bültena, L. (2025, January 10). Ist das 1,5-Grad-Ziel noch machbar? *quarks.de*. <https://www.quarks.de/umwelt/klimawandel/1-5-grad-ziel/>
- COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 2008/120/EC of 18 December 2008 Laying down Minimum Standards for the Protection of Pigs, 47 L (2008). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32008L0120>
- Deutscher Tierschutzbund e.V. (n.d.). *Milchkühe in der Landwirtschaft*. Deutscher Tierschutzbund e.V. Retrieved 12 January 2025, from <https://www.tierschutzbund.de/tiere-themen/tiere-in-der-landwirtschaft/rinder/milchkuehe>
- European Commission. (2020). *Farm to Fork Strategy: For a fair, healthy and environmentally friendly food system*. European Commission. https://food.ec.europa.eu/document/download/472acca8-7f7b-4171-98b0-ed76720d68d3_en?filename=f2f_action-plan_2020_strategy-info_en.pdf

- European Commission. (2022a, February 24). *Factsheet – a greener and fairer CAP*. European Commission. https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/document/download/89b607ec-8a43-4073-bafd-f2493da7699e_en?filename=factsheet-newcap-environment-fairness_en.pdf&prefLang=de
- European Commission. (2022b, October 4). *COMMISSION STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE FITNESS CHECK*. European Commission. https://food.ec.europa.eu/document/download/74ba158a-d778-4b96-885e-35a1e550a646_en?filename=aw_eval_revision_swd_2022-329_en.pdf
- European Commission. (2023, November 23). *REPORT FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND THE COUNCIL*. European Commission. https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/document/download/6b1c933f-84ef-4b45-9171-debb88f1f757_en?filename=com-2023-707-report_en.pdf&prefLang=de
- European Commission. (2024a). *Milk and milk product statistics*. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Milk_and_milk_product_statistics
- European Commission. (2024b, December 20). *CAP at a glance—European Commission*. https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy/cap-overview/cap-glance_en
- European Council. (2019). *European Green Deal*. Consilium. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/green-deal/>
- European Parliament. (2016, December). *Präzisionslandwirtschaft und die Zukunft der Landwirtschaft in Europa*. EPRS | Wissenschaftlicher Dienst des Europäischen Parlaments. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2016/581892/EPRS_STU\(2016\)581892_DE.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2016/581892/EPRS_STU(2016)581892_DE.pdf)
- European Union. (n.d.). *Folgen des Klimawandels—Europäische Kommission*. Offizielle Website der EU. Retrieved 14 January 2025, from https://climate.ec.europa.eu/climate-change/consequences-climate-change_de
- FAO. (2024). *Agricultural production statistics* (Booklet No. 96; FAOSTAT Analytical Briefs). Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. <https://openknowledge.fao.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/df90e6cf-4178-4361-97d4-5154a9213877/content>
- Feindt, P. H., Krämer, C., Früh-Müller, A., Heißenhuber, A., Pahl-Wostl, C., Purnhagen, K. P., Thomas, F., Van Bers, C., & Wolters, V. (2019). *Ein neuer Gesellschaftsvertrag für eine nachhaltige Landwirtschaft: Wege zu einer integrativen Politik für den Agrarsektor*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-58656-3>
- Fetting, C. (2020). *THE EUROPEAN GREEN DEAL* (ESDN Report). ESDN Office.

- Fusco, G. (2021). Twenty Years of Common Agricultural Policy in Europe: A Bibliometric Analysis. *Sustainability*, 13(19), 10650. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su131910650>
- Gavinelli, A. (2013). *EU Animal Welfare policies*. <https://mlr.baden-wuerttemberg.de/fileadmin/redaktion/m-mlr/intern/Gavinelli.pdf>
- German Ethics Council. (2020, June 16). *Tierwohllachtung – Zum verantwortlichen Umgang mit Nutztieren*. Deutscher Ethikrat. file:///C:/Users/h-ale/Downloads/stellungnahme-tierwohllachtung.pdf
- German Parliament. (n.d.). *Deutscher Bundestag—Was ist Nachhaltigkeit?* Deutscher Bundestag. Retrieved 27 January 2025, from https://www.bundestag.de/ausschuesse/weitere_gremien/pbne/vorstellung/was-ist-nachhaltigkeit-890694
- GoClimate. (2022, December 8). *Die Drei Säulen der Nachhaltigkeit | GoClimate*. <https://www.goclimat.de/glossar/drei-saeulen-der-nachhaltigkeit/>
- Greenpeace. (2024, October). *SCHMUTZIGES GEHEIMNIS: SO HEIZT DIE MILCH- UND FLEISCHINDUSTRIE DAS KLIMA AN*. Greenpeace. https://www.greenpeace.de/publikationen/20241007_Greenpeace-Report_SchmutzigesGeheimnis_f.pdf
- Hackbarth, D. (2024, April 18). *Neokolonialismus mit Nestlé*. Die Wochenzeitung. <https://www.woz.ch/taeglich/2024/04/18/neokolonialismus-mit-nestle>
- Heyl, K., Döring, T., Garske, B., Stubenrauch, J., & Ekardt, F. (2021). The Common Agricultural Policy beyond 2020: A critical review in light of global environmental goals. *Review of European, Comparative & International Environmental Law*, 30(1), 95–106. <https://doi.org/10.1111/reel.12351>
- Hoekstra, A. (2010). *THE GREEN, BLUE AND GREY WATER FOOTPRINT OF FARM ANIMALS AND ANIMAL PRODUCTS* (Study No. 48; VALUE OF WATER RESEARCH REPORT SERIES). UNESCO-IHE Institute for Water Education. <https://www.waterfootprint.org/resources/Report-48-WaterFootprint-AnimalProducts-Vol1.pdf>
- humanrights.ch. (2005, July 22). *Nestlé angeklagt wegen Zwangsarbeit für Kinder—Humanrights.ch*. humanrights.ch. <https://www.humanrights.ch/de/ipf/menschenrechte/wirtschaft/nestle-angeklagt-zwangsarbeit>
- iDMC. (2024). *Global Report on Internal Displacement*. <https://api.internal-displacement.org/sites/default/files/publications/documents/IDMC-GRID-2024-Global-Report-on-Internal-Displacement.pdf>
- INA. (2024). *2024: Top-Thema 10 -*. <http://www.derblindefleck.de/2024-top-thema-10/>
- Kropp, A. (2019). Die Dimensionen der Nachhaltigkeit. In A. Kropp, *Grundlagen der Nachhaltigen Entwicklung* (pp. 11–12). Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-23072-2_4

- Kubon, I. (2022, October 21). *Was ist Massentierhaltung und welche Probleme verursacht sie?* PETA Deutschland e.V. <https://www.peta.de/themen/massentierhaltung/>
- Mahlerwein, G. (2020, September 24). *Strukturwandel und Agrarentwicklung seit 1880*. bpb.de. <https://www.bpb.de/themen/umwelt/landwirtschaft/316059/strukturwandel-und-agrarentwicklung-seit-1880/>
- Mayring, P., & Fenzl, T. (2019). Qualitative Inhaltsanalyse. In N. Baur & J. Blasius (Eds.), *Handbuch Methoden der empirischen Sozialforschung* (pp. 633–648). Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-21308-4_42
- Nachhaltigkeit Wirtschaft. (2024, January 6). *Global vs. Lokal: Wie sichert man Versorgung in einer globalisierten Welt?* Nachhaltigkeit Wirtschaft. <https://nachhaltigkeit-wirtschaft.de/globalisierte-produktion-versus-lokaler-sicherer-versorgung/>
- Nienaber, B. (2012). Die erste Transformation der europäischen Landwirtschaft: Von der naturbezogenen zur industriellen Produktion. In *Europa- eine Geographie* (pp. 252–257). University of Luxembourg. https://orbilu.uni.lu/bitstream/10993/10832/1/europanienaberkapitel4.1_fertig.pdf
- Pe'er, G., Finn, J. A., Díaz, M., Birkenstock, M., Lakner, S., Röder, N., Kazakova, Y., Šumrada, T., Bezák, P., Concepción, E. D., Dänhardt, J., Morales, M. B., Rac, I., Špulerová, J., Schindler, S., Stavrínides, M., Targetti, S., Viaggi, D., Vogiatzakis, I. N., & Guyomard, H. (2022). How can the European Common Agricultural Policy help halt biodiversity loss? Recommendations by over 300 experts. *Conservation Letters*, 15(6), e12901. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12901>
- PETA. (2023, February 15). *Wasserverbrauch für Fleisch: Wie hoch ist er wirklich?* PETA Deutschland e.V. <https://www.peta.de/themen/wasserverbrauch-fleisch/>
- PETA. (2024, October 4). *Kuhmilch: Die wichtigsten Infos zu Tierleid, Gesundheit & Umwelt*. PETA Deutschland e.V. <https://www.peta.de/themen/kuhmilch/>
- Public Eye. (2024, June). PUBLIC EYE MAGAZIN. In *Mexiko Wächst Die Wut Auf Nestlé*, 48. https://www.publiceye.ch/fileadmin/doc/Magazin/2406_PublicEye_Magazin_48_DE_96_dpi.pdf
- Purvis, B., Mao, Y., & Robinson, D. (2019). Three pillars of sustainability: In search of conceptual origins. *Sustainability Science*, 14(3), 681–695. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-018-0627-5>
- Roth, M. (2021, February). *Prävalenz und Prädiktoren von Burnout, Depression und Angst bei Landwirten und Landwirtinnen in Deutschland und Österreich*. Paris-Lodron-Universität Salzburg. file:///C:/Users/h-ale/Downloads/StudieMariaVONUNI.pdf
- Schlachthof transparent. (n.d.). *Schlachthof transparent: Statistik*. Retrieved 12 January 2025, from https://www.schlachthof-transparent.org/pages/statistik.php?utm_

- Statista. (2023). *Armutgefährdungsquote Migrationshintergrund 2023*. Statista. <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/436197/umfrage/armutsgefaehrdungsquote-in-deutschland-nach-migrationshintergrund/>
- Stucki, S. (2023, January 20). *Die Fleischfrage im aktuellen Klima*. Max-Planck-Gesellschaft. <https://www.mpg.de/19766823/essay-fleischkonsum-und-klimaschutz>
- Swiss Holdings. (2012, December). *Die Schweiz und ihre Konzerne*. Verband der Industrie- und Dienstleistungskonzerne in der Schweiz. <https://swissholdings.ch/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Die-Schweiz-und-ihre-Konzerne.pdf>
- Tillich, M. (2017, June 1). *Bottled Life: Die Wahrheit über Nestlés Geschäfte mit dem Wasser*. Utopia.de. https://utopia.de/bottled-life-nestles-geschaefte-mit-wasser_12072/
- VSF International. (2024, October). *Agrarökologie und „One Health“*. VSF International. https://www.vsf-international.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/3_VSF-Agroecology-One-health_deutsch-final.pdf?utm_
- Weingarten, P. (2021, April 8). *Die Entwicklung der Gemeinsamen Agrarpolitik der EU*. bpb.de. <https://www.bpb.de/themen/umwelt/landwirtschaft/327284/die-entwicklung-der-gemeinsamen-agrarpolitik-der-eu/>
- WHO. (2023, October 23). *One Health*. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/one-health>
- Wilke, S. (2013a, July 16). *Treibhausgas-Emissionen in der Europäischen Union* [Text]. Umweltbundesamt; Umweltbundesamt. <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/daten/klima/treibhausgas-emissionen-in-der-europaeischen-union>
- Wilke, S. (2013b, August 7). *Beitrag der Landwirtschaft zu den Treibhausgas-Emissionen* [Text]. Umweltbundesamt; Umweltbundesamt. <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/daten/land-forstwirtschaft/beitrag-der-landwirtschaft-zu-den-treibhausgas>
- WWF. (2014). *Fleisch frisst Land* (No. 4). WWF Germany. https://www.wwf.de/fileadmin/fm-wwf/Publikationen-PDF/WWF_Fleischkonsum_web.pdf?utm
- WWF. (2023, October 9). *(Massen-)Tierhaltung: Folgen für Tier, Mensch & Klima*. <https://www.wwf.de/themen-projekte/landwirtschaft/massentierhaltung>